

CONNIE'S METANOIA OVER DEPRESSION: A RELIGIOUSLY-INTEGRATED COGNITIVE BEHAVIORAL THERAPY CASE STUDY

Jose Leonardo L. Degillo, PhD, RGC, LPT, RPsy¹
and
Meraly S. Degillo, MA, RGC, LPT²

*¹College of Arts and Sciences, Kabankalan Catholic College, Kabankalan City,
Philippines*

*²Social Sciences Department, West Visayas State University, Himamaylan City,
Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10931347>

ABSTRACT

The case study examines Connie's experience with the Religiously-Integrated Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (RCBT). Data collection and analysis involve inductive, exploratory, interview, counseling session documentation, and content analysis. This is also a theological paper that uses the see-judge-act method, popularized by Pope John XXIII, to promote critical thinking and reflection on social situations. Connie, a Filipino professional teacher, recalled and faced devastating life events during the COVID-19 pandemic, which significantly impacted her mental health. The strict quarantine regulations forced Connie to miss school and church activities and social contact, feeling isolated and drained of memories. Connie, despite receiving weekly inspirational verses and prayers, continued to experience low mood and intrusive thoughts despite seeking help from her churchmates and pastor. She experienced psychological symptoms such as fear of infection, depression, anxiety, social isolation, and stigma, and was diagnosed with Major Depressive Disorder. Connie's thoughts of painful memories and extreme sadness recur, even if she was under medication already. Connie's 14-month counseling (RCBT) focused on addressing the separation from parents and depression, using cognitive reframing and mindfulness-based interventions. The counseling relationship was terminated based on Connie's progress. The intervention, i.e., RCBT, was found effective and beneficial for Connie. Consequently, the study affirms that faith formation,

family support, and access to mental health professional were crucial for Connie's healing journey.

Keywords: *case study, see-judge-act, metanoia, depression, counseling*

INTRODUCTION

The case of Connie is one of the many cases of Filipino professionals, who have faced devastating life events, yet are still church faithful, and quests for mental health and general wellbeing. The COVID19 pandemic have worsen the scenario, detrimental effects on the mental health of Filipinos were significantly noticed. In one study, they have investigated on the mental health impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on respondents who have been quarantined since March 2020, aiming to determine if COVID stress predicts common mental health issues like stress, depression, and anxiety (Montano & Acebes, 2020).

Strict quarantine regulations, in effect for nearly a year, have forced close-knit families to be isolated; religious festivals have been abandoned, and churches have been forced to limit attendance; and schools have been closed (Dancel, 2021). Connie was among those who were pluck off from her usual routine of being in school, since she is a professional teacher, missed church activities and personal contact with churchmates, and felt isolated due to the restrictions and time mostly spent at the boarding house alone. These instances gave her more time to think, to recall, and eventually led her to remember dreaded memories and realities in her life.

During the recent epidemics and pandemic like COVID19, SARS, MERS, and Ebola, the fear of infection or death, helplessness, depression, anxiety, social isolation, and stigma are the most commonly reported psychological manifestations (Wafula et al., 2023). These psychological manifestations took toll on the life of Connie. She got so worried about the thoughts, especially memories, that occupies her mind most of the time. The teleconsultation with a psychiatrist gave her the opportunity to be diagnosed with Major Depressive Disorder and received medication.

She recounted that the medication gave her time to rest, relax, and sleep. The first-line treatment for depression is often a class of drugs called selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs), which work by increasing serotonin levels in the brain, a critical neurotransmitter that promotes communication between nerve cells (Schreiber, 2023). But once the medication's effect tone down, she would easily return to her intrusive thoughts of painful memories and extreme sadness. To put things in context, depression is a global public health concern causing disability, higher morbidity, mortality, and medical costs, with 60% of individuals receiving effective medications, with response rates decreasing in comorbid conditions (Pearce et al., 2015).

She resorted to seeking the assistance of her churchmates and pastor. Religious and spiritual interventions are frequently viewed as a supplementary therapeutic option; since Christianity is one of the most popular religions, we concentrated on it here as the spiritual intervention (Leung & Li, 2023). However, the preparedness and promptness of providing the apt intervention for the current cares, concerns, and conditions of Connie were not met by these people. According to her, they gave her weekly inspirational and scriptural verses, and prayed for her, but to no avail, she would continue her low mood and hang on to her intrusive thoughts for the whole week up until she would visit the church again on a Sunday, once major restrictions were lifted.

After seeking assistance from a psychiatrist, a pastor, and fellow parishioners, Connie still feels that there is something wrong, there is something lacking. It is by this time, that a fellow teacher, her confidant, encouraged her to meet with a mental health professional so as to go through in-person counseling and psychotherapy.

This referral made it possible for Connie to meet me, a licensed counselor. She wrote on the form that records the main goal of the counseling session, "I want peace." The quest for Connie's peace is the problem that this study aims to record and report, and which the interventions through counseling have addressed.

Healing Journey. The World Health Organization recommends holistic interventions for those with mental health issues, so as to establish general health and wellness for the public in the biological, psychological, social, and spiritual domains (Degillo & Gayoles, 2020). Noteworthy to point though is the reality of communities facing systematically greater barriers to healthcare because of low access to primary and behavioral healthcare (Holt, Kibicho, & Bell-Calvin, 2022).

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant effect on people's mental health and overall wellbeing (Barbieri et al., 2022). The COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in challenges, including health inequalities, low health information literacy, shed light on government incompetence, and pervasive disinformation with detrimental effects on health (Jennings-Roche et al., 2023). During this wearisome times, mental health services faced challenges in delivering care, often utilizing telemental health technologies like phone and video calls (Luke et al., 2022). Also, the closure of churches and reduced participation in religious practices led to the proposal of indirect participation through the media (Dobosz et al., 2022). Overall, the COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted health systems globally, the Philippines for one, leading to reduced access to essential and non-essential health services due to lockdowns, travel restrictions, and staffing disruptions (Okunogbe et al., 2023).

Healing and recovery for those who are going through difficulties is deemed necessary, especially to those who are facing the ripple effects caused by the recent pandemic. On one hand, healing, a widely used concept in healthcare, is culture-dependent and requires a clear understanding of its applications which varies from different cultures and communities. Watson's theory, for example, emphasizes the

importance of healing, promoting healing through caring-healing modalities like music, therapeutic touch, aromatherapy, and relaxation. These interventions help relieve pain, accelerate wound healing, improve physical symptoms, and reduce chemotherapy side effects (Sadat-Hoseini et al., 2023). On the other hand, recovery has a tripartite understanding: clinical, personal, and social. Clinical recovery involves full symptom remission from mental illness, while personal recovery focuses on social aspects and psychiatric treatment. Personal recovery is a distinct process involving social aspects, partial remission despite residual symptoms, and minimal psychiatric treatment, both incorporate clinical aspects. Social recovery involves residential and economic independence (Nielsen, Buus, & Berring, 2023). For this study, pursuing the healing and recovery of Connie is important.

Religiously-integrated cognitive behavioral therapy. In the field of pastoral counseling, the religiously-integrated cognitive behavioral therapy is hypothesized to be beneficial for Connie. RCBT is a manualized therapeutic method that uses religious beliefs, practices, and resources to help individuals develop thoughts and behaviors that reduce depression (Pearce et al., 2015). Religiously integrated cognitive behavioral therapy (RCBT) uses religious traditions to improve well-being by replacing unhelpful thoughts and behaviors. Studies have shown its effectiveness in treating depression and anxiety in patients with various religious backgrounds (Degillo & Gayoles, 2020). Research indicates that incorporating spiritual and religious beliefs in therapy can reduce depression (Pearce et al., 2015).

Humans strive for complete health, addressing diverse factors through various perspectives like psychiatry, psychotherapy, and spiritual traditions in enhancing physical and mental health (Buju, 2019). The use of spiritually-integrated and religiously-integrated therapy has been in practice for quite some time. The study of de Abreu & Moreira-Almeida (2022), for example, analyzed randomized clinical trials comparing religion-adapted cognitive behavioral therapy (R-CBT) with control conditions in psychiatric disorder clients, utilizing their adapted manuals for data extraction. In addition, the study of Pečecnik & Gostečnik (2022), a systematic overview of research was presented on the use of spirituality as a potential treatment method for depression. Also, the study of Saged-Ali et al. (2022) explored the effectiveness of a religiously designed Islamic intervention in reducing depression and anxiety disorders among Muslim patients using a randomized controlled trial design. Furthermore, religion and spirituality are often integrated into treatment for addiction, HIV risk behavior, depression, and cancer, using spirituality-based therapies like Spiritual Self-Schema, mindfulness, and coping groups (Pearce et al., 2015).

These examples of the integration of psychological and spiritual innervations have shown remarkable and replicable initiatives in helping people heal and recover, leading to the betterment of their current mental health status.

Mental health status. Mental health is crucial for overall well-being, influenced by individual, social, cultural, and systematic stress sources (Madhani et al., 2023).

Meanwhile, the World Health Organization defines health as a comprehensive state of physical, mental, and social wellbeing, not just the absence of disease or infirmity (Aziz, Raines, & Wuensch, 2023). Consequently, in the present practice, spiritual wellbeing is acknowledged, hence making it as the biopsychosocialspiritual approach to wellbeing (Tan, 2023). In practice, mental health professionals emphasize the importance of incorporating spirituality in therapy, but often miss the mark to regularly assess and address this aspect in treatment planning (Charzyńska & Heszen-Celińska, 2020). Nonetheless, transforming mental illness into mental wellness has become sensible solutions and supports human sustainability in general (Crosby & Robertson, 2022).

The absence of mental wellness and interventions in the workplace for example, can jeopardize functioning and developing industries. The construction industry, for instance, is facing a surge in mental health disorders, leading to reduced work ability, increased accident and injury risk, and a potential "perfect storm" of mental health issues (Greiner et al., 2022). In the school setting as well, mental health wellness can be compromised if interventions could not be found. College students, for example, face numerous challenges during their transition from adolescence to emerging adulthood, including identity development, sexuality, substance abuse, grief, loss, family dysfunction, and changes in values. Stressors include new living arrangements, homesickness, academic achievement, time management, and social maladjustments. 85% of college students regularly feel overwhelmed, which can be linked to mental health conditions. Academic pressure and existing mental health conditions are among the top reasons for college students experiencing mental health problems (Kratt & Houdyshell, 2020).

The Philippines' first mental health act legislation, Republic Act no. 11036, was signed into law in June 2018, providing a rights-based framework for optimal mental healthcare implementation (Lally, Samaniego, & Tully, 2019). Aside from the approval of the Mental Health act and the experience of COVID-19 pandemic that altered the public interest in mental health in the Philippines, religion and spirituality can be potential resources for mental health (Del Castillo, Del Castillo, & Koenig, 2023; Alibudbud, 2022). The Philippines, with its largest Christian population of 109 million, is deeply rooted in Catholicism. With almost 80% of Filipinos practicing the Roman Catholic faith, the country is the world's third-largest Catholic country. However, religion in the Philippines is not monolithic, with various beliefs including Christian, Islam, Buddhism, and Sikhism. Interreligious dialogues, rooted in the Filipino value of *pakikipagkapwa* (fellowship), contribute to community building and social cohesion. Most Filipinos consider religion essential in their lives, and studies show that it positively impacts mental health, relationships, academic success, and well-being. Some Filipino women use spirituality to interpret events and make decisions (Del Castillo, Del Castillo, & Koenig, 2023).

Objectives of the Study

This case study aims to present the following:

- a) describe and discuss life context of Connie that led her this this healing journey,

- b) explore and explain the contributions of the religiously-integrated cognitive behavioral therapy in the process of Connie gaining insights and improvements in her mental health status,
- c) and make meaningful connections between the experiences of Connie and the psycho-spiritual approach used in this case study.

Relevance of the Study

This study creates relevance in the fields of psychology and theology through the following means:

- a) providing points for describing and discussing a person's healing journey,
- b) rendering reasons and realities that explore and explain the contributions of the religiously-integrated cognitive behavioral therapy in the process of gaining insights and improvements in one's mental health status,
- c) and making meaningful connections between the experiences of struggle and the psycho-spiritual integration.

METHODOLOGY

This is a qualitative single case study; a nonrandom sampling method was done, purposively selecting the single case of Connie (Myers, 2019; Ames, Glenton, & Lewin, 2019). Consequently, the collection and analysis of qualitative data, involves searching for the inductive, exploratory, interview, focus groups, sampling textual or visual content from the Internet, content analysis, thematic analysis, and inductive coding that corresponds to the systematic analysis of Connie's case (Özen & Mittelstädt, 2023). The case study-qualitative methodologies will be enhanced by pertinent literature reviews (Murkin et al., 2022).

Moreover, to establish depth on the insights and reflections of this study, the see-judge-act method shall be utilized. The "see, judge, act" formula, popularized by St. Pope John XXIII, involves examining the situation, evaluating it according to church teachings, and then deciding what actions should be taken, requiring accurate judgment and seeing (Cloutier, 2023). Furthermore, see-judge-act encourages critical-thinking and reflection on social situations, focusing on moral sensibility which engages and incorporates social justice traditions from Scripture, magisterial documents, and related sources (Kawulok, 2020). Thus, from a single case, the case of Connie (not her real name) facts and findings are recorded and reported hereon.

See. Connie is a public-school teacher. She is serving one of barangays near the city. For about almost a decade now she is actively working in the teaching profession. The first five years, she served a private school, and then found a greater employment opportunity with the public schools' system in the country. She has been performing her profession well, able to support her family's needs, and study a master's degree. When the pandemic started, all of these changed.

After two months of isolation due to health protocols, Connie has not been performing her profession well, got fed up with supporting her family's needs, and study a master's degree. Moreover, the Covid19 pandemic gave her more time to think about her past. Thoughts and emotions related to being unvalued, and being abused came alive.

Thoughts and emotions related to being unvalued was rooted in her experience of being left to the care of her grandmother days after she was born because her parents decided to live separate lives. As she was growing up, she was always questioning her value. Self-talking like, "Am I not important, that is why they left me behind?" "Maybe I am not really important. Maybe my birth is the reason why they separated. Maybe I am the cause of their separation." Thoughts of being unvalued became intrusive that she could not focus in doing her work as a teacher, in doing the adjustments demanded by the pandemic to professional teachers—i.e., distant learning. Emotions of sadness deregulated into depression due to the ample amount of time she is spending in thinking that she is unvalued.

Connie knew by then that she needs to take actions related to what she is going through. The first group that she approached were her churchmates. Fellow church goers became her confidants. Listened to her and prayed for her. The church's pastor listened to her, gave advice, and scriptural reflections. By this time, community gathering was highly restricted. Video calls and phone calls were the most reliable means of communication at that moment. This constant sharing gave relief to her during and sometime after the moments of communication. This cycle went on until such time that the government allowed minimal and regulated congregation gathering in churches and other public places. She noticed though that intense thoughts, emotions, and actions were happening before and would resurface sometime after the encounter with churchmates.

The second person she approached was a psychiatrist, through a virtual consultation. The psychiatrist conducted a thirty-minutes online assessment. She was diagnosed with a major depressive disorder. An antidepressant was given to her as medication. With that she diligently took her medicine. She recounted though that once the relaxing and calming effect of the medicine ceases, intrusive thoughts and emotions come back.

The third group that she approached were her workmates. Some of her workmates already knew her life story before the pandemic happened. This group became her confidant. When public school teachers were asked to return to school and prepare for distance learning strategies, they also noticed that Connie was not performing well, like she was doing before. There were even incidents in school that Connie broke down in tears. At times she was observed to be in total silence for the whole day. Her workmates got worried. One of them, had a background in guidance and counseling, encouraged her to see licensed counselor. That workmate introduced her to the author of this paper, a

practicing licensed counselor in the city of Kabankalan. This introduction led to the development of a year and two months counseling process.

Judge/Discern. In the counseling process using the Religiously-Integrated Cognitive Behavioral Therapy, there are four essential documents: (1) Counseling Relationship Form, (2) Direction and Objectives Form, (3) Interventions and Progress Form, and (4) Relationship Termination Form. These documents record and report her metanoia, healing journey.

The Counseling Relationship Form contains three major parts. First, the agreement of pursuing the client's formation and growth as a human person. Second, the presentation and acknowledgement of the clients that they are receiving a professional practice that is regulated and delivered through a licensed counseling professional. Third, this form secures the agreement and commitment of the counselor and the counselee in the counseling process by affixing their respective signature.

Connie and the counselor affixed their signatures and started with the counseling process by determining the direction and objections.

The Direction and Objectives Form records the main goal or direction of the counseling process as discerned by the counselee, and agreed upon by the counselor. The main goal is something that the counselee wants to achieve as an end result of this counseling process. While the objectives are the initial steps or the initiated steps taken by the counselee to reach the main goal.

The counselee noted that she wanted to achieve peace in her life, that is what she has written on the section for the main goal. The steps that she has taken so far involved (a) seeking refuge to her church community, (b) seeking assistance from a psychiatrist, and (c) seeking support from her workmates, her friends.

The Interventions and Progress Form has three major parts: (1) the objectives anchored on the experience of the counselee, (2) the interventions explained and recommended by the counselor that aims to assist counselees in addressing, adjusting, or achieving their objectives, and (3) the progress as reported by the counselee and verified by the counselor as accomplished, partially accomplished, or not accomplished.

During the fourteen months counseling process there were a total of seven major issues-interventions-insights that can be drawn from the Interventions and Progress Forms of Connie. But for the purpose of this case study, we shall only use two.

The first one is on Connie's reality of being a child of parents who decided to live separate lives. Connie felt hurt because of this reality. Ever since she became conscious of this reality she also started to question her worth. (1) As part of the counselee's objectives anchored on this experience, the peace that she seeks as her main goal, may find its manifestation later on once she resolves her thoughts, feelings, and behaviors

related to this parents' separation reality. (2) It was explained to Connie that in order to resolve her thoughts, feelings, and behaviors attached to her parents' separation reality, there is a need to explore and explain her interpretations of this reality. It was found out that Connie associated the experience with the thoughts being unworthy, the feelings of sadness, and the actions of being aloof, untrusting, and unappreciative. Cognitive reframing was used as an intervention. It is also known as cognitive restructuring, is a method that replaces negative thoughts with more realistic, helpful ones. (Rogers, 2021). After addressing and adjusting her thoughts about the said reality, the counselee was able to achieve her goal. This adjustment was epitomized by her realization that she was looking for love, worth, and being accepted from people who were not there, but love, worth, and being accepted were always given to her by no less than her grandmother. *Lola* has always been there. Fed her, and took care of her daily needs. Hugged her and kissed her. Stayed beside her, guided, and supported her up until fourth year high school. (3) *Ara gali si Lola. Ara gid siya gali.* This realization of her grandmother's loving presence reported by the counselee is verified. The intervention accomplished the aim and led the counselee to progress.

The second one is on how Connie shall manage attacks of sadness (this is how she calls the experience). Friends and co-workers would notice that she exhibits slowing down in her physical and mental functions at school. She would event attest that at the moments of attack she would loss of focus and loss of motivation to do something. Psychomotor retardation and loss of energy can be observed (APA, 2022). When feelings of worthlessness and inappropriate guilt visits her ability to think and concentrate diminishes because of these thoughts of death arise. Hurting oneself and suicidal ideation happened to Connie. (1) She wanted to help herself. Connie knew that something needs to be done, so that she may not worsen the situation. There is more to life than just being succumbed to depression because of the uncontrollable realities of life. She felt inside her and understood that she can do better. Her faith and hope say so. But she does not know how to concretely do it, so to speak. (2) Mindfulness-based interventions, such as meditation, and walking, can help reduce depression (Liu et al., 2023). Several sessions were dedicated to practice mindfulness exercises, such as mindfulness breathing and mindfulness walking, until such time she was ready to used them in real life scenarios. Mindfulness breathing strategies enhance cognitive functioning, reduce stress, and improve classroom behavior in teachers (Hall, 2023). This technique was also used by outside of the classroom, at her boarding house, or in any place where she would feel the trigger of the attack. In one instance, Connie recounted that she was able to assist a student who suddenly screamed and cried while attending a limited face-to-face class. She thought the student the breathing technique that helped her as well. The counselee was happy to recall that experience, and retell how she benefited from that technique as well. (3) She emphasized that, *"Kaya ko gali magkasubo pero wala ginasakit akon kaugalingon."* (It is now possible for me to feel sadness without hurting myself.)

In her progress report, the counselee was encouraged to continue with her faith practices of praying and attending church services, while reaping the benefits of practicing the interventions recommended to her during the counseling sessions. It is also noted

that, she would bring in scripture readings and insights at various moments of the sessions. Her prayers have been constantly noticed as the core of her quest for peace. Prayer, a personal communication with God, has been linked to improved mental health among Christians, easing anger, sustaining love, multiplying joy, and granting forgiveness (Del Castillo, Del Castillo, & Koenig, 2023). At the first instance of raising the desire to seek professional help through counseling, through prayers she had courage and took the essential steps for her healing journey. This same faithful counselee remained steadfast in the counseling process, and claimed her progress one session at a time. On the fourteenth month she was able to claim her desired goal, peace.

The last document is the Relationship Termination Form. The counselee and counselor both agreed that the time has come to terminate the counseling relationship. The resolve was not based on any false hope, such that there will be no problems, issues, or relapse that will happen to the counselee. Instead, the resolve was grounded on (1) the new skillset of the counselee to manage better her thoughts, feelings, and actions, (2) healthy practices through mindfulness exercises and interventions, and (3) insights drawn from cognitive reframing activities that led her to value her worth, forgive her parents, and inspire resilience for herself, to all those dear to her, and those who she professionally serves as a teacher. A study found spirituality positively impacts mental health, but differed in scope and roles (He & Petrakis, 2023). In this case of Connie, spirituality led her to this counseling process and sustained her up to this very moment of termination. *“Mas kusog ang akon paminsaron, kumpara sa bulong.”* (My thoughts are stronger than the medication.) This conviction sums up the counseling process.

Metanoia is the spiritual process involving existential transformation of being Christ-like in intellect, will, and human action (Sonea, 2023). Connie's act of being able to convert from her depression is a concrete manifestation of metanoia. The head, heart, and hands of Connie, so to speak, were able to move from the illness side of the spectrum to the wellness side of it.

Act. Religions offer a comprehensive understanding of self and the world, reducing isolation and loneliness, and through symbolic teachings and prayers, individuals cope with personal challenges (Leira, 2023). This context is the foundation of Connie's quest for healing—the quest for peace, the quest for converting her lifestyle into a lifestyle makes her experience peace. Managing depression, gaining a better life narrative, and having effective mindfulness skillsets paved the way for Connie to experience healing, experience peace, the peace she desired.

Healing is a holistic process involving patients forming a deep relationship with themselves and therapists, aiming for balance in physical and non-physical dimensions, and implementing desired developmental changes (Sadat-Hoseini et al., 2023; Stevens, 2019). In Connie's case, she was able to achieve her counseling goal, and that was made possible because she was open to the counseling process, had a good prior spiritual foundation, and had established good rapport and a therapeutic relationship with her counselor.

The following realities became essential to Connie's healing journey: (a) faith formation and foundation, (b) love and belonging felt from her grandmother, churchmates, workmates, and friends, and (c) access to mental health professionals, i.e., psychiatrist (online), and counselor/psychologist (in-person).

Mental health issues in the Philippines, including anxiety and depression, are a significant challenge, requiring non-health sectors like education, church, and social welfare to promote overall well-being (Del Castillo, Del Castillo, & Koenig, 2023). The availability of faith and mental health structures are essential in the holistic intervention and prevention approach to mental health issues and disorders (Pečečnik & Gostečnik, 2022).

Hence, it is highly recommended that (a) churches, schools, and homes become venues for faith formation and foundation. (b) Also, each person deserves to experience love and belonging from family members, churchmates, workmates, and friends. (c) Lastly, access to professionals and persons who can adequately provide interventions aiding people in their biological, psychological, social, and spiritual needs (Madhani et al., 2023).

Acknowledging what are available at the moment in churches, schools, and homes confirms that we are not starting from scratch on the intervention level. Noteworthy to say as well is the calling for the improvement on the possible prevention, intervention, and postvention programs and services that could transpire out of these discoveries found on this case study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Connie, a Filipino professional teacher, faced devastating life events during the COVID-19 pandemic, highlighting the mental health impacts on Filipinos (Del Castillo, Del Castillo, & Koenig, 2023; Alibudbud, 2022). The strict quarantine regulations forced families to isolate, religious festivals to be abandoned, and schools closed. Connie missed church activities and personal contact, feeling isolated and drained of memories and realities. This case study aimed to explore and explain Connie's metanoia over depression through the aid of Religiously-integrated Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (Degillo & Gayoles, 2020).

During the COVID-19 pandemic, Connie experienced fear, depression, anxiety, social isolation, and stigma. She was diagnosed with Major Depressive Disorder and received medication, which helped her relax and sleep. SSRIs, a first-line treatment, increased serotonin levels in the brain, but Connie's thoughts of painful memories and extreme sadness returned once the medication's effects decreased (Schreiber, 2023).

Connie sought help from her churchmates and pastor, who were viewed as a supplementary therapeutic opportunity. Despite providing weekly inspirational verses and prayers, they futile in addressing her current cares and concerns. Connie continued to experience low mood and intrusive thoughts until major COVID-19 restrictions were lifted.

Connie, despite seeking help from psychiatrists, pastors, and parishioners, still felt unwell. Her confidant encouraged her to seek in-person counseling and psychotherapy. A licensed counselor met her, and the study aims to record and report the interventions she received.

The intervention given to the client was based on the principles and practices of Religiously-Integrated Cognitive Behavioral Therapy counseling process involves four essential documents: Counseling Relationship Form, Direction and Objectives Form, Interventions and Progress Form, and Relationship Termination Form. The Counseling Relationship Form outlines the client's metanoia journey, acknowledges professional practice, and secures commitment between counselor and counselee through signatures.

The Counseling Relationship Form outlines the client's commitment to personal growth, acknowledgement of professional counseling practice by a licensed professional, and their respective signatures, which are crucial for the counseling process, including determining direction and objections.

The Direction and Objectives Form outlines the main goal of a counseling process, determined by the counselee and agreed upon by the counselor. The objectives are the initial steps taken to achieve the main goal, such as seeking refuge to her church community, assistance from a psychiatrist, and support from workmates and friends.

The Interventions and Progress Form consists of three main parts: objectives based on counselee's experience, counselor-recommended interventions, and progress reported by counselee and counselor. This case study focuses on two of the seven major issues, interventions, and insights from Connie's 14-month counseling process, based on her Interventions and Progress Forms.

The main focus was on Connie's separation from her parents, which led to feelings of hurt and self-questioning. The counselee aimed to find peace by resolving her thoughts, feelings, and behaviors related to this reality. Cognitive reframing was used as an intervention to replace negative thoughts with more realistic ones (Rogers, 2021). Connie realized that she was seeking love, worth, and acceptance from her grandmother, who provided her with love, support, and guidance. This realization led to progress and the realization of her grandmother's loving presence.

Connie struggles with depression, causing slowing down in her physical and mental functions at school. She experiences loss of focus, motivation, and psychomotor retardation. Feeling worthless and guilt, she loses her ability to think and concentrate. This leads to hurting herself and suicidal ideation. Connie seeks help and believes she

can do better. Mindfulness-based interventions, such as meditation and walking, can help reduce depression (Liu et al., 2023). Connie practices mindfulness exercises, such as mindfulness breathing and walking, to enhance cognitive functioning, reduce stress, and improve classroom behavior.

The counselee's progress report highlights her faith practices, including prayer and church attendance, and the interventions recommended during counseling sessions. She incorporates scripture readings and insights into her sessions, focusing on prayer as a core for her quest for peace. Through prayer, she gained courage and progressed, eventually achieving her desired goal of peace in the fourteenth month.

The counselor and counselee have decided to terminate their counseling relationship, based on the counselee's new skills, healthy practices, and cognitive reframing activities (Rogers, 2021). The counselor values her worth, forgives her parents, and inspires resilience. Connie's spirituality has led her to this counseling process and sustained her through the termination, as her thoughts are stronger than medication.

Metanoia is a spiritual process involving existential transformation, as demonstrated by Connie's conversion from depression, moving her body and mind from illness to wellness.

Religions provide a holistic understanding of self and the world, reducing isolation and loneliness. Connie's quest for healing, based on managing depression, improving life narrative, and mindfulness skills, led to her desired peace. Healing involves forming a deep relationship with therapists, aiming for balance, and implementing developmental changes. Connie's success was made possible by her openness, prior spiritual foundation, and therapeutic relationship.

Connie's healing journey was facilitated by faith formation, love and belonging from her family, and access to mental health professionals, both online and in-person.

Mental health issues in the Philippines, such as anxiety and depression, require non-health sectors like education, church, and social welfare to promote overall well-being (Del Castillo, Del Castillo, & Koenig, 2023; Alibudbud, 2022; Lally, Samaniego, & Tully, 2019). Faith and mental health structures are essential for holistic intervention and prevention, with churches, schools, homes, and professionals providing necessary interventions.

Scriptural Insights. Healing is a common theme in the Sacred Scriptures. In relation to the experience of Connie, there are three Gospel stories that could shed insights and inspirations to the readers of this case study. They are as follows: (1) Healing of the Crippled Woman (Luke 13:10-13), (2) Healing the Sick in Gennesaret (Mark 6:53-56), and (3) Healing of Simon's Mother-in-Law (Luke 4:38-39).

Healing of the Crippled Woman. Jesus was teaching in a synagogue when he saw a woman with a crippled spirit for 18 years. Jesus freed her, and she immediately stood up straight and began praising God (NRSVUE, 2024, Luke 13:10-13).

And just then there appeared a woman with a spirit that had crippled her for eighteen years. She was bent over and was quite unable to stand up straight (Luke 13:11). For eighteen years the crippled woman dealt with this reality. Many years of being bent over by this spirit, making her unable to stand straight. This scenario of the crippled woman is very relatable to Connie. Connie dealt with the reality of being born to parents who decided to live separate lives. She took this reality in, and was led to a crippling realization, as it were. She thought that she was worthless, that she was the cause of her parents' separation, and that life means less because of this reality. She maximized the negativity of the situation, and ended up listening and prioritizing the promptings of the crippling spirit, so to speak.

The crippled woman appeared on the area where Jesus was, it is such an opportune time. With our any hesitation, Jesus *called her over and said, "Woman, you are set free from your ailment (Luke 13:12)."* The Providence of the Divine abounds! Amidst the limitation of healing the woman, as the crowd sees it improper, Jesus willed that there and then the woman be set free from that which cripples her. In comparison to Connie's scenario, the pandemic was somehow a life-changing event that nobody expected to happen and have such drastic effects. But it happened. Due to the pandemic, Connie had an ample time to be off her daily routines that made her somewhat forget her past and crippling thoughts, emotions, and behaviors. This disruption led her to navigate once more to the dark pages of her past. The Providence of the Divine abounds! Amidst the seeming turmoil that Connie experienced, these experiences opened the door for a new form of intervention that led her to healing. An opportune time, which introduced her and sustained her in pursuing freedom from that which cripples her, and pursue better self-management, better narration of her past, and peace in life.

When he laid his hands on her, immediately she stood up straight and began praising God (Luke 13:13). Healed by Jesus, the once crippled woman stood up straight and went about praising God, proclaiming the Good News. She became a testimony of Jesus' goodness, the experience of being healed by God. In my professional practice, Connie is a concrete testimony of a healing experience through a psycho-spiritual intervention. All glory and praise belong to God, who made this healing journey possible for Connie, and for all those clients have benefited and will benefit from this psycho-spiritual intervention known as Religiously-integrated Cognitive Behavioral Therapy.

Healing the Sick in Gennesaret. After crossing the river, they landed at Gennesaret and moored their boat. People recognized them and brought sick people to their villages, cities, or farms. They asked for the fringe of their cloak to be touched, and all healed (NRSVUE, 2024, Mark 6:53-56).

When they had crossed over, they came to land at Gennesaret and moored the boat. When they got out of the boat, people at once recognized him (Mark 6: 53-54). The people knew that Jesus and his disciples heal. His words and works are becoming renowned. Preaching the Gospel and healing the sick became the groups' identity, so when people knew where they are a multitude of crowd gathers. Connie also knew. She had faith and hope in Jesus. Since her grandmother introduced faith, love, and hope to her, she knew that Jesus is her refuge, especially in times of life's difficulties and disasters. She maintained the composure of faith and hope as she sought assistance from her churchmates and pastor. She carried faith and hope in her heart as she sought the assistance of a psychiatrist, and took her medication. She sustained her faith and hope as she ventured through counseling, desired and developed healthy coping mechanisms, thoughts, feelings, and actions, and eventually attained the peace she aimed for.

Instrumental to her healing process, as well, are her colleagues at work, especially the one who suggested to her that she needs to see a licensed counselor, so as to provide an in-person assistance. This experience of care and concern was also experienced by those *sick on the mats* who were *rushed and brought to Jesus wherever they heard he was (Mark 6:55)*. The people who genuinely care for us, who find ways, extend their means, and assist us in finding the peace and healing we are longing for. Connie was blessed to have colleagues, turned friends, genuinely cares for her—people who would go an extra mile, *pray with us and beg for us*, so to speak, in order for us to experience peace and healing (Mark 6:56).

Healing of Simon's Mother-in-Law. After leaving the synagogue, he entered Simon's house, where his mother-in-law was suffering from a high fever. He rebuked her, and she woke up and began serving (NRSVUE, 2024, Luke 4:38-39).

After leaving the synagogue he entered Simon's house. Now Simon's mother-in-law was suffering from a high fever, and they asked him about her (Luke 4:38). Simon was clear with what he is praying for, the healing of his mother-in-law. Connie was clear as well, she wanted to do better and be able to attain peace. The prayer for doing better came about in the form of better narratives of the past, healthy coping strategies, and better self-care techniques. Peace came about once she was able to acknowledge love from her grandmother through awareness, love for herself through self-care, and love for those who hurt her through forgiveness and kindness.

Then he stood over her and rebuked the fever, and it left her. Immediately she got up and began to serve them (Luke 4:39). Jesus heals. In response to Jesus' goodness, Simon's mother-in-law was moved to service. In gratitude, she got up and began to serve them. In the story of Connie, she had been an instrument for the healing of herself, for parents, for her family, and for those whom she serves as a professional teacher. Being able to experience healing, Connie through the process of counseling have dedicated six months of connecting and reconciling with both of her parents. She was also able to reconnect to her siblings from both sides. Questions, thoughts, and emotions that she has kept for the longest time has been delivered in ways better than she could ever

imagine. Her resolve for peace, paved the way for other members of the family to quest for peace as well. Furthermore, Connie became an instrument for her students to quest for their own healing journey as well. She would teach them ways and means to manage their lives better by care for themselves and practice healthy coping strategies. In gratitude, Connie too got up and began to serve those dear to her and those who are entrusted under her care.

Promoting the Gospel Values. Connie was healed. The pandemic led her to seek healing through Religiously-integrated Cognitive Behavioral Therapy. Connie's healing journey was influenced by her faith in Jesus, seeking help from churchmates, pastors, psychiatrists, and medication. The journey involved praying and practicing healthier means for her to experience peace. Her healing journey has been a testament to the power of faith, love, and compassion. Through counseling, she reconciled with her family and herself, and her resolve for peace has inspired others.

This case study is a testimony to the Gospel values of faith, hope, and love through the healing experience of Connie. Faith has been the foundation for Connie's experience of healing to happen. The faith she mustered and manifested through difficult and developing moments became an apt and ample resource for her for love and peace. Love in the experience of Connie might have a seeming absence due to her life's context, but it motivated her to do better in life. The hope of attaining peace, accompanied her in the quest for healing. With God's grace, her participation to the counseling process, and with essential people, metanoia became possible.

Conclusions

The case study of Connie, showcased a Filipino professional teacher who experienced severe mental health impacts during the COVID-19 pandemic. She was diagnosed with Major Depressive Disorder and received medication, but her thoughts of painful memories and extreme sadness returned. Despite seeking help from her churchmates and pastor, Connie continued to feel unwell. Her confidant encouraged her to seek in-person counseling and psychotherapy.

The Religiously-Integrated Cognitive Behavioral Therapy was used as a psycho-spiritual intervention for Connie. This counseling process involved four essential documents: Counseling Relationship Form, Direction and Objectives Form, Interventions and Progress Form, and Relationship Termination Form. The counseling process focused on Connie's separation from her parents, leading to feelings of hurt and self-questioning. Cognitive reframing was used as an intervention to replace negative thoughts with more realistic ones. Connie also sought love, worth, and acceptance from her grandmother, who provided her with love, support, and guidance.

In Connie's struggled with depression, mindfulness exercises became effective in responding to her acts of slowing down in her physical and mental functions at school. Mindfulness-based interventions, such as meditation and walking, were used to reduce

depression. Connie's progress report highlighted the therapeutic effects that benefited her through the therapy practices and interventions combined with her faith practices, including prayer and church attendance.

Connie's healing journey was facilitated by faith formation, quest for love and belongingness, and access to mental health professionals. Mental health issues in the Philippines require the integration of health and non-health sectors like education, church, and social welfare to promote overall well-being. Churches, schools, and homes should serve as faith formation venues, provide love and belonging to individuals, and offer access to professionals for interventions addressing biological, psychological, social, and spiritual needs.

Recommendations

It is recommended that churches, schools, and homes serve as faith formation venues, provide love and belonging to individuals, and offer access to professionals for interventions addressing biological, psychological, social, and spiritual needs (Aziz, Raines, & Wuensch, 2023; Tan, 2023; Madhani et al., 2023). The case study highlights the need for enhancement of prevention, intervention, and postvention programs and services based on the findings.

The study found that Connie's healing journey was significantly influenced by faith formation, family support, and access to mental health professionals, resulting in the effectiveness of RCBT.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The participant was once a counseling client of the researcher. During the orientation about the counseling service that she intends to receive, it was explained to her that the counselor shall use RCBT as basis for principles and practices in counseling. She was also informed that the counseling center is also into research and development, hence her data, without disclosing her name, will be kept confidential but will be available for research so as to contribute in the advancement of the counseling profession and practice in the country. She committed to the counseling process by affixing her signature to the informed consent and the counseling relationship form.

No conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study. The researchers have reviewed the study and guarantee that plagiarism was firmly avoided. Moreover, due credit is given to Pearce et al for RCBT. The intervention used in the counseling process and in this study is heavily anchored on the principles and practices of RCBT. Connie benefited from RCBT by pursuing this therapeutic method that used religious beliefs and practices to help individuals develop thoughts and behaviors that reduce depression, and manage their lives better.

Results are purely for research use only.

Acknowledgements

Gratitude is duly given to St. Camillus de Lellis for inspiring us to continue serving as mental health professionals who witness the ever-present love of Christ to all, especially to those whom we serve.

Gratitude is also given to the priests of Little Way College Seminary for allowing us to use their facilities during our counseling and mental health sessions.

Gratitude is similarly given to our mentors, students, and fellow mental health professionals who motivates us to advance our expertise.

Gratitude is given to our family especially to our sons Jeo Leandro and Deo Kamilo for blessing us with the opportunity to practically and purposefully conduct counseling, mental health programs, and researches.

REFERENCES

- Alibudbud, R. (2022). Googling “mental health” after mental health legislation and during the COVID-19 pandemic: An infodemiological study of public interest in mental health in the philippines. *Journal of Mental Health, 31*(4), 568-575. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/09638237.2022.2091757>
- American Psychiatric Association. (APA) (2022). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders* (5th ed., text rev.). <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.books.9780890425787>
- Ames, H., Glenton, C., & Lewin, S. (2019). Purposive sampling in a qualitative evidence synthesis: A worked example from a synthesis on parental perceptions of vaccination communication. *BMC Medical Research Methodology, 19* doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-019-0665-4>
- Aziz, S., Raines, J. M., & Wuensch, K. L. (2023). An email-based workplace health intervention: Failures, lessons learned, and guidance for future research. *Journal of Organizational Psychology, 23*(2), 58-69. Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/email-based-workplace-health-intervention/docview/2831825615/se-2>
- Barbieri, V., Piccoliori, G., Mahlknecht, A., Plagg, B., Ausserhofer, D., Engl, A., & Wiedermann, C. J. (2023). Adolescent mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic: The interplay of age, gender, and mental health outcomes in two consecutive cross-sectional surveys in northern italy. *Behavioral Sciences, 13*(8), 643. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/bs13080643>
- Buju, S. (2019). Clinical approach of spiritual illnesses: Eastern christian spirituality and cognitive behavioral therapy. *Pastoral Psychology, 68*(4), 361-378. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11089-019-00874-5>
- Charzyńska, E., & Heszen-Celińska, I. (2020). Spirituality and mental health care in a religiously homogeneous country: Definitions, opinions, and practices among polish mental health professionals. *Journal of Religion and Health, 59*(1), 113-134. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10943-019-00911-w>
- Cloutier, D. (2023). See, judge, act. *U.S.Catholic, 88*, 40-41. Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/magazines/see-judge-act/docview/2763592746/se-2>
- Crosby, P., & Robertson, S. (2022). Transforming mental illness into mental wellness. *Cincinnati Enquirer* Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/newspapers/transforming-mental-illness-into-wellness/docview/2665453310/se-2>
- Dancel, R. (2021). An epidemic of despair as crippling as covid-19: Virus has taken toll on Filipinos’ mental health as they worry over rising infections, finances. *The Straits Times* Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/newspapers/epidemic-despair-as-crippling-covid-19/docview/2537252095/se-2>
- de Abreu, C. M., & Moreira-Almeida, A. (2022). Religion-adapted cognitive behavioral therapy: A review and description of techniques. *Journal of Religion and Health, 61*(1), 443-466. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10943-021-01345-z>
- Degillo, J.L., & Gayoles, L.A. (2020). The Effect of Religiously Integrated Cognitive Behavioral Therapy on the Psycho-Spiritual Well-Being of People Living with HIV.
- Del Castillo, F. A., Del Castillo, C. D., & Koenig, H. G. (2023). Associations between prayer and mental health among Christian youth in the Philippines. *Religions, 14*(6), 806. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/rel14060806>
- Dobosz, D., Gierczyk, M., Janiak, A., Piasecki, D., & Rajba, B. (2022). Transformations of religiosity during the SARS-CoV-2 Pandemic—On the example of catholic religious practices of polish students. *Religions, 13*(4), 308. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/rel13040308>
- Greiner, B. A., Leduc, C., Clodhna O’Brien, Cresswell-Smith, J., Rugulies, R., Wahlbeck, K., . . . Aust, B. (2022). The effectiveness of organizational-level workplace mental health

- interventions on mental health and wellbeing in construction workers: A systematic review and recommended research agenda. *PLoS One*, 17(11)
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0277114>
- Hall, C. A. (2023). Mindfulness breathing strategies to reduce teacher stress: A mixed method study (Order No. 30690060). Available from ProQuest Central; Publicly Available Content Database. (2878253914). Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/mindfulness-breathing-strategies-reduce-teacher/docview/2878253914/se-2>
- He, L., & Petrakis, M. (2023). Spiritual diversity in personal recovery from mental health challenges: A qualitative study from Chinese Australian service users' perspectives. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(3), 2210. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20032210>
- Holt, J. M., Kibicho, J., & Bell-Calvin, J. (2022). Factors that sustained the integration of behavioral health into nurse-led primary care. *Community Mental Health Journal*, 58(8), 1605-1612. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10597-022-00976-0>
- Jennings-Roche, A., Adle, M., Jean, B. S., & Jaeger, P. T. (2023). The 1918 influenza pandemic in popular media and the roles of public libraries in supporting health information access, health literacy, and health justice during pandemics: Learning from the past to prepare for the future. *The Library Quarterly*, 93(1), 86-109. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1086/722550>
- Kawulok, D. M. (2020). See, judge, act: Catholic social teaching and service learning. rev. ed. by erin M. brigham,. winona, MN: Anselm academic, Christian brothers publication s, 2019. 219 pages. *Horizons*, 47(2), 364-365. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1017/hor.2020.78>
- Kratt, D., & Houdyshell, M. (2020). Student teachers and mental health: A qualitative study on students' experiences living with a mental health condition. *Journal of Social, Behavioral and Health Sciences*, 14, 4. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5590/JSBHS.2020.14.1.05>
- Lally, J., Samaniego, R. M., & Tully, J. (2019). Mental health legislation in the Philippines: Philippine mental health act. *BJPsych International*, 16(3), 65-67. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1192/bji.2018.33>
- Leira, C. (2023). How devout Catholics use religious symbols and religious teachings to cope during personal challenges (Order No. 30637493). Available from ProQuest Central; Publicly Available Content Database. (2860548477). Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/how-devout-catholics-use-religious-symbols/docview/2860548477/se-2>
- Leung, J., & Li, K. (2023). Faith-based spiritual intervention for persons with depression: Preliminary evidence from a pilot study. *Healthcare*, 11(15), 2134. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare11152134>
- Luke, S. R., Dalton-Locke, C., Landau, S., Needle, J. J., & Johnson, S. (2022). Variations in the uptake of telemental health technologies in community and crisis mental health services during the early pandemic: A survey of mental health professionals in the UK. *BMC Psychiatry*, 22, 1-19. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-022-04385-1>
- Madhani, F. I., Tompkins, C., Jack, S. M., & Byrne, C. (2023). Perceptions of mental health among pakistani women with micro-finance loans: An interpretive descriptive study. *The Qualitative Report*, 28(8), 2401-2420. doi:<https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2023.6198>
- Montano, L. T., & Acebes, K. M. L. (2020). Covid stress predicts depression, anxiety and stress symptoms of Filipino respondents. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 9(4), 78-103. doi:<https://doi.org/10.20525/ijrbs.v9i4.773>
- Murkin, C., Rooshenas, L., Smart, N., Daniels, I. R., Pinkney, T., Shabbir, J., . . . Blencowe, N. S. (2022). What should be included in case report forms? development and application of novel methods to inform surgical study design: A mixed methods case study in parastomal hernia prevention. *BMJ Open*, 12(10) doi:<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2022-061300>

- Myers, D. E. (2019). The experiences and perceptions of stress of administrative personnel: A qualitative single case study (Order No. 22584623). Available from ProQuest Central. (2284530869). Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/experiences-perceptions-stress-administrative/docview/2284530869/se-2>
- New Revised Standard Version Updated Edition (NRSVUE). (2024). Bible Gateway. <https://www.biblegateway.com/>
- Nielsen, J. M., Buus, N., & Berring, L. L. (2023). Mental health recovery in social psychiatric policies: A reflexive thematic analysis. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(12), 6094. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20126094>
- Okunogbe, A., Meekins, M., Saalim, K., Mary Angeli Conti-Lopez, Rosario, M. B., Mendoza, O. M., . . . Bisson, C. (2023). Utilization of adolescent health services during the COVID-19 pandemic: Evidence on impact and adaptations from a rapid assessment survey in the Philippines. *BMC Public Health*, 23, 1-10. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-023-15102-2>
- Özen, O., & Mittelstädt, A. (2023). Mixed methods in research on the psychology of the internet and social media. [Mixed Methods in der Forschung zur Psychologie des Internets und sozialer Medien] *Forum : Qualitative Social Research*, 24(1) doi:<https://doi.org/10.17169/fqs-24.1.4009>
- Pearce, M. J., Koenig, H. G., Robins, C. J., Nelson, B., Shaw, S. F., Cohen, H. J., & King, M. B. (2015). Religiously integrated cognitive behavioral therapy: a new method of treatment for major depression in patients with chronic medical illness. *Psychotherapy (Chicago, Ill.)*, 52(1), 56–66. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0036448>
- Pečečnik, T. M., & Gostečnik, C. (2022). Use of spirituality in the treatment of depression: Systematic literature review. *Psychiatric Quarterly*, 93(1), 255-269. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s1126-020-09881-9>
- Rogers, M. (2021). Reframing your future: A cognitive reframing curriculum to reduce recidivism through inmate education (Order No. 28861357). Available from ProQuest Central; Publicly Available Content Database. (2605222156). Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/reframing-your-future-cognitive-curriculum-reduce/docview/2605222156/se-2>
- Sadat-Hoseini, A., Shareinia, H., Pashaeypoor, S., & Mohammadi, M. (2023). A cross-cultural concept analysis of healing in nursing: A hybrid model. *BMC Nursing*, 22, 1-12. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-023-01404-8>
- Saged-Ali, A. G., Sa'ari, C. Z., Abdullah, M. b., Al-Rahmi, W., Ismail, W. M., Zain Mohamed, I. A., & alShehri Nourah bint Abdullah, bin Mtaib. (2022). The effect of an Islamic-based intervention on depression and anxiety in Malaysia. *Journal of Religion and Health*, 61(1), 79-92. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10943-021-01484-3>
- Schreiber, A. (2023). The most common depression medications, explained. *The Times - Tribune* Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/newspapers/most-common-depression-medications-explained/docview/2819478035/se-2>
- Sonea, C. S. (2023). Theosis and Martyria—The spiritual process of deification and its implication for the mission of the church. *Religions*, 14(1), 12. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/rel14010012>
- Stevens, M. N. (2019). Clients in counseling: How clients report counseling changes their everyday life (Order No. 27670456). Available from ProQuest Central; ProQuest Dissertations & Theses A&I; ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (2410785635). Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/clients-counseling-how-report-changes-their/docview/2410785635/se-2?accountid=28547>
- Tan, S. (2023). Applying theology in the psychology classroom: Reflections on integration in the trenches for 35 years. *Journal of Psychology and Christianity*, 42(1), 59-68. Retrieved from

<https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/applying-theology-psychology-classroom/docview/2825575576/se-2>

Wafula, S. T., Ninsiima, L. L., Mendoza, H., Ssempebwa, J. C., Walter, F., & Musoke, D. (2023). Association between recent COVID-19 diagnosis, depression and anxiety symptoms among slum residents in kampala, uganda. PLoS One, 18(5)
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0280338>